

An appraisal of the effectiveness of corpus linguistic research feedback: Healthcare professionals' perceptions

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This study investigates the impact of corpus linguistic feedback on healthcare professionals, particularly within cosmetic surgery consultations. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the research integrates quantitative corpus analysis with qualitative insights to examine linguistic patterns, such as stigmatising discourse, medical vs. lay terminology, and interactional asymmetry. The study involves data from three UK healthcare sites. Key findings reveal a significant use of lay terms by surgeons, an unexpected prevalence of patient interruptions, and the perpetuation of stigma through language. Feedback was provided to surgeons via an executive report, followed by their evaluations through questionnaires and debriefings. Results indicate that linguistic feedback heightened awareness among surgeons, prompting reflections on communicative practices and intent to implement changes. This study underscores the utility of corpus linguistics in enhancing healthcare communication and makes a contribution to the field of applied linguistics through the appraisal and recommendations offered for improving patient-centred care and communication.

Keywords: Applied Linguistics; Corpus Linguistics; Cosmetic Surgery; Healthcare Communication; Medical Discourse

1. Introduction

Effective communication in healthcare settings is paramount for successful patient outcomes and overall satisfaction. The complexity of medical discourse, particularly in specialised medical areas poses unique challenges. Indeed, as the landscape of healthcare continues to evolve, the need for nuanced understanding and effective communication between healthcare providers and patients has become increasingly evident. Communication serves as the backbone of the doctor-patient relationship, enabling the exchange of information, the building of trust, and the clarification of patient concerns. As Brookes and Hunt (2021) emphasise, the significance of situated communication in healthcare contexts cannot be understated; it is through dialogue that therapeutic goals are established, and health outcomes are influenced.

In this vein, this paper explores how corpus linguistics can illuminate communication dynamics within the medical context. By examining the intricacies of these interactions, the study aims to offer insights into the epistemological factors that influence discourse within this field. Furthermore, the nature of communication in cosmetic surgery consultations through a mixed-method approach is evaluated, contributing to the discourse on effective linguistic practices in healthcare. The findings will not only shed light on the intricacies of communication in cosmetic surgery but also aim to inform broader applications in healthcare communication practices.

2. Background

2.1. Theoretical framework of communication in healthcare

The discourse surrounding healthcare has evolved, recognising the role of communication as a fundamental component of patient care. Roter and Hall (2006) assert that ‘talk’ is essential for crafting the doctor-patient relationship, while Hunt (2021) emphasises the prevalence of spoken interactional routines in healthcare. The literature suggests that all communicative acts within healthcare, be they verbal or non-verbal, constitute healthcare discourse that is influenced by various epistemological factors (Gotti et al., 2015).

Understanding these dynamics is crucial in a healthcare context where miscommunication can lead to adverse outcomes. Theoretical frameworks such as conversation analysis and discourse analysis offer valuable lenses through which to explore these interactions. Conversation analysis, in particular, delves into the nuances of turn-taking, interruptions, and the sequential organisation of talk, highlighting how these features shape the flow of communication in medical consultations (Maynard, 1991). Discourse-based analysis of healthcare instead examines the interactions which take place from a more contextualised and global perspective (Brookes & Hunt, 2021; Padley, 2022a).

2.2. Communication and interaction in healthcare settings

Healthcare communication is multifaceted, encompassing a range of interactions that are not only medical but also social. According to Roberts and Sarangi (2003), applied linguistics in healthcare settings can serve as a problem-solving tool, addressing real-life communication challenges. The complexity of doctor-patient interactions is well-documented, with studies utilising discourse analysis (West, 1984) and conversation analysis (Maynard, 1991) to unpack these dynamics. Recent studies in corpus linguistics have also provided additional layers of understanding, focusing on quantifiable language use within healthcare contexts (Brookes & Baker, 2022; Mullany, 2007).

The role of effective communication in healthcare cannot be overstated. It not only facilitates the transmission of medical knowledge but also fosters patient engagement and empowerment. A strong doctor-patient relationship, built on trust and clear communication, is essential for ensuring adherence to medical advice and enhancing patient satisfaction. Therefore, investigating the intricacies of healthcare discourse is crucial for identifying areas of improvement in communication practices.

2.3. Cosmetic surgery discourse

Despite the advancements in understanding healthcare communication, the realm of cosmetic surgery has remained relatively underexplored, particularly in terms of interactive discourses. The literature has primarily focused on multimodal discourse in advertising (Lirola & Chovenec, 2012; Moran & Lee, 2013), neglecting the interactive aspects of consultations. This study addresses this gap by analysing communication within cosmetic surgery settings, highlighting how language shapes patient experiences and perceptions.

In the context of cosmetic surgery, communication takes on a unique significance. Patients seeking cosmetic procedures often grapple with societal expectations and personal desires, making the consultation process highly sensitive (Padley, 2024). Indeed, the language used by both healthcare professionals and patients can significantly influence the outcomes of these consultations. By understanding the discursive strategies employed in these interactions, it is possible to identify how communication impacts patient perceptions, motivations, and satisfaction with surgical outcomes.

2.4. Applied linguistics and healthcare discourse

Applied linguistics and corpus linguistics methodologies have significantly influenced the understanding of healthcare communication, offering deep insights into how language shapes interactions between healthcare providers and patients (Brookes & Collins, 2023; Roberts, 2003). One key area of impact is the analysis of patient-practitioner discourse, which is central to diagnosing issues, understanding patient concerns, and guiding treatment plans (Sarangi, 2010). Brookes and Hunt (2021) explore how discourse analysis in healthcare settings can identify linguistic patterns that either facilitate or obstruct communication, such as the use of directives, mitigations, and explanations. These linguistic features are crucial in creating a sense of patient involvement and trust, with corpus analyses revealing recurring patterns of misunderstanding that can lead to reduced patient adherence to medical advice. Similarly, Baker's (2006; 2023) work on using corpora to analyse health-related texts has highlighted the importance of understanding how institutional language can

sometimes alienate patients, particularly when medical jargon is used excessively.

Beyond these works, other researchers have expanded the scope of applied linguistics to examine the impact of linguistic choices on health outcomes. For instance, Candlin and Sarangi (2004) have investigated how language mediates professional healthcare relationships, showing that interactions often revolve around asymmetrical knowledge structures, where healthcare professionals hold expert authority over patients. Their work underscores the need for a more patient-centred communication approach, particularly in sensitive contexts such as end-of-life care or chronic illness management. Candlin and Sarangi's research suggests that an applied linguistic lens can help reframe these conversations by promoting more collaborative dialogues, wherein patients feel empowered to voice their concerns and preferences. This shift from a paternalistic model to one of shared decision-making (Di Pace & Padley, 2024) has been a focal point in improving patient outcomes and satisfaction.

In addition, Atkins (2019) conducted a study that specifically analysed healthcare professionals' communication skills through role-play, comparing simulated consultations to real-life interactions in general practice. Using interactional analysis, Atkins identified key differences between these environments, particularly in how clinicians managed patient expectations and emotional cues. The study showed that in simulated settings, healthcare professionals were more likely to adhere to scripted, idealised responses, whereas real-life consultations required more adaptive communication strategies. This highlights the importance of training medical professionals in realistic communication scenarios. Combined with studies by Roberts and Sarangi (2003) on gatekeeping encounters, as well as Egbert and Baker's (2020) work on corpus linguistic triangulation, Atkins' findings contribute to a growing body of applied linguistic research that seeks to enhance the quality and effectiveness of healthcare communication, ultimately contributing to better patient care and equitable health outcomes.

In light of the above literature, this study seeks to further the investigation into corpus linguistic methodologies used to analyse healthcare discourses (Brookes & Collins, 2023) within the context of cosmetic surgery. Furthermore, there is a particular focus placed on the extent to which the results can be rendered tangible to the non-linguist healthcare professionals.

2.5. Study aims

This research project formed part of a larger doctorate investigation which considered the following four macro areas:

1. Expert/Non-expert Identities: an exploration of the language used in consultations, examining the motivations, psychological factors, and stigma associated with cosmetic surgery.
2. Lexical Impact: assessment of the impact of lexicon on interactional features, utilising quantitative corpus data to define linguistic characteristics.
3. Interactional Asymmetry: investigation of the extent to which interactional asymmetry may exist in the corpus by analysing the power dynamics within consultations.
4. Applicability of Results: Evaluate the applicability of findings to the fields of Language for Specific Purposes (LSP) and healthcare communication practices.

This particular paper offers an overview of how a selection of the results from the abovementioned areas were adapted and provided to the healthcare professionals and what their perception of the linguistic feedback was. Furthermore, it provides insights into how the feedback has influenced their communicative practice and/or drawn attention to features of their communication that they were unaware of. This paper also reflects on the methodologies used for applied linguistics and whether these can be replicable and tangible to future linguistic/communicative healthcare investigations.

3. Method

3.1. Study design

The study adopted a mixed-methods approach, integrating quantitative and qualitative analyses to provide a comprehensive view of communication in cosmetic surgery consultations. Drawing on corpus linguistic analysis, corpus-based discourse analysis, and ethnographic methods (McEnery & Hardie, 2012; Sarangi, 2006; Stubbe et al., 2021), the research aimed to yield tangible insights into the communicative practices of healthcare professionals.

A mixed-methods design allows for a richer understanding of communication dynamics by combining numerical data with contextual insights. This approach not only facilitates the identification of patterns within the corpus but also enables a deeper exploration of the meanings and implications behind those patterns. Indeed, it also allows for the triangulation of data (Egbert & Baker, 2020).

In line with applied linguistics, the concept of 'effective linguistics' (Sarangi, 2006) was applied to this project with an eye to provide tangible linguistic observations to the clinical participants through an executive report and debriefing (McMahon & Winch, 2018). Furthermore, the feedback provided to the healthcare professionals was also envisioned within the framework of

ethnography (Gumperz, 1999; Sarangi, 2006; Stubbe et al., 2021) whereby the role of the analyst is forefront (Roberts, 2003). In particular, the analyst is able to emerge themselves within the professional context (Duranti & Goodwin, 1992) and be accepted as a part of the (discourse) community (Swales, 1990) in order to gain a greater understanding and insight into the linguistic context under examination. This was achieved in this study through the researcher being accepted as a 'semi-expert' in the field by both patients and healthcare providers due to their professional and academic background working within the field of healthcare. Hence, the feedback provided is considered not only to be of a linguistic nature but also multidisciplinary, as it addresses communication based on the premise of linguistics while also considering other factors such as professional communication (Sarangi, 2006), context (Duranti & Goodwin, 1992) as well as the transferability of linguistic results to the healthcare field (Brookes & Collins, 2023; Candlin & Sarangi, 2004).

3.2. Participants and data collection

Data were collected from three healthcare sites across the UK—Nottinghamshire, Cambridge, and Royal Tunbridge Wells—between September 2021 and March 2022. A total of 36 patient consultations were recorded, transcribed, and analysed, resulting in 257,274 tokens and 23,388 sentences.

The consultations were selected based on their relevance to cosmetic surgery, ensuring a diverse range of cases and patient demographics. Ethical considerations were paramount in this study, with all participants providing informed consent (health practitioners and patients alike) and assurances of confidentiality. Anonymity of the patients was guaranteed by the researcher. Indeed, the recordings were anonymised, and sensitive information was carefully managed and stored in order to maintain participant privacy.

3.3. Analysis

The analysis for the doctoral project employed both qualitative and quantitative methods. Lexical analysis was conducted using software tools such as Sketch Engine and #LancsBox, while statistical analyses, including the *Chi-Squared* Test, were applied to assess the significance of findings. The study focused on key themes such as stigmatising discourses, medical terminology use, as well as interruptions within consultations.

Quantitative Analysis: The quantitative analysis provided a statistical overview of linguistic features, enabling the identification of significant trends and patterns in the data. This dual approach allowed for triangulation, ensuring that the findings were robust and well-supported by evidence.

Qualitative Analysis: The qualitative analysis involved a close examination of transcriptions to identify patterns in language use, communication strategies, and the construction of meaning. Discourse analysis techniques were employed to uncover the subtleties of interaction and the social dynamics at play during consultations.

In order to disseminate the results to the clinical participants, an executive report was written which provided:

1. An initial overview of the salient findings in the first pages in order to orientate the participants as regards the study aims and initial linguistic observations.
2. A glossary of important linguistic terms which included clarification regarding corpus linguistics as a methodology and also terms such as concordances and keyness.
3. An outline of detailed quantitative findings including statistical analysis and graphs.
4. Excerpts of their transcribed dialogues in order to provide concrete examples.

In order to gather the clinicians' perception of the utility of the feedback, an online questionnaire was distributed to the participants which used both multiple choice questions and open questions. Following the distribution of the questionnaire, online debriefing sessions were organised with the participants in order to provide clarification regarding the feedback and to ascertain whether the healthcare professionals had made any modifications to their communicative practice.

4. Results

4.1. Overview of findings

The analysis carried out for the doctorate project yielded several key linguistic findings that illuminate the nature of communication in cosmetic surgery consultations and that were shared with the healthcare professionals.

The first set of results regarded stigmatising discourses whereby patients often expressed a desire to hide their surgical procedures, revealing a pervasive stigma associated with cosmetic surgery. The language used reflected a reluctance to disclose surgical history, with many patients opting for euphemisms or alternative justifications for their procedures. Furthermore, the healthcare professionals themselves also alimented the same stigma by encouraging patients to hide their procedures and striving to obtain unnoticeable results (Padley, 2024).

Furthermore, in many consultations, there were instances where patients would articulate their desires for surgery in terms of enhancing personal appearance or addressing specific physical issues rather than directly stating their intentions. This pattern highlights the complex interplay between personal motivations and societal perceptions of cosmetic surgery, as patients navigate their own desires within the context of potential stigma (Padley, 2024).

The second area of salient results regards the lexical patterns identified within the corpus. The study found a significant prevalence of lay terminology used by surgeons, despite their expertise, as well as by patients (89% vs 11% of lay terms used respectively). This choice was statistically significant ($p < 0.00001$), suggesting that surgeons may prioritise patient comprehension over technical accuracy. A case in point includes terms such as 'tummy tuck' and 'facelift' which were frequently used instead of their clinical counterparts (abdominoplasty and rhytidectomy), indicating an awareness of the need for clear communication (Padley, 2025).

However, despite lay terminology dominating, there was still a high prevalence of medical terminology ($n = 628$ terms) identified and used by the surgeons. Furthermore, the analysis also revealed that surgeons often provided explanations for medical terms, adapting their language to suit the patients' level of understanding. They also used illustrations to support their clarifications where necessary. This adaptability was deemed to be crucial in establishing rapport and ensuring that patients felt informed about their procedures (Padley, 2025).

A third important area identified for communication involved the extent to which the interactions were symmetrised or otherwise. Aside from the use of medical lexis vs laity, interruptions between both parties as a measure of asymmetry were also investigated. Surprisingly, contrary to initial expectations, patients interrupted surgeons more frequently (55% vs 45%). Indeed, these findings challenge traditional notions of power dynamics within healthcare consultations. The unexpected prevalence of patient-initiated neutral or relational interruptions (Goldberg, 1990) suggests a more collaborative dialogue than might typically be assumed in medical settings (Fairclough, 1989).

Indeed, an example of this can be seen in instances where patients would interrupt surgeons to clarify details about their procedures or to express their concerns, demonstrating active engagement in the conversation. This challenges the notion of a unidirectional flow of information, emphasising the importance of patient agency in consultations (Fage-Butler & Anesa, 2016).

The final aim of the doctoral project was that of applying the findings to the field of Language for Specific Purposes as well as the field of healthcare communication. The first step has already been trialed in the English for Medical Purposes classroom where authentic materials (extracted from the corpus) were used for teaching purposes. The findings highlight the pedagogical utility of authentic materials in training future healthcare professionals (i.e., medical students) in order to improve their knowledge of scientific English, enhance their awareness of communicative practices and, hence, encourage more patient-centred approaches (Padley, 2022b). Based on these findings, it was deemed that the data collected can be utilised in educational contexts, informing curricula for medical professionals and contributing to improved communication strategies.

Therefore, the final applicability of the results to the field of linguistics regards the way in which the previously mentioned results were deemed to be of use to the healthcare practitioners involved in the project. Their impressions were collected through an online questionnaire as well as online debriefing sessions and can be consulted in the following section.

4.2. Relevance of findings transferred into tangible feedback

The participating surgeons were provided with an executive summary which outlined the key findings in a user-friendly fashion (i.e., avoiding linguistic terminology deemed of little relevance to physicians). This involved providing an overview of salient findings and then more detailed results in the subsequent sections and appendices.

The main areas which were drawn to the participants' attention are in line with the abovementioned findings from the doctoral project:

1. Language used within the consultations making reference to the stigmatisation of cosmetic surgery.
2. The way in which medical lexis is employed within the corpus (including statistical analysis of its use) and whether this may impact on interactional asymmetry.
3. The way in which interruptions are classified and quantified within the consultations, also considered as a measure of potential interactional asymmetry (including statistical analysis of its use).

The feedback regarding these points was gathered primarily via an online questionnaire and, at a later date, during online debriefing meetings. In terms of the first research finding, physicians stated that they were in fact surprised (67%) to discover that striving for natural results, which would not be noticeable, increases the stigma attached to cosmetic surgery (Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Pie Chart Illustrating the Surgeons' Impressions of Language Contributing to Stigmatising Cosmetic Surgery

While there are studies which hypothesise the extent to which cosmetic surgery has been stigmatised by the media (Patel, 2010) and indeed there is a culture of publicly shaming celebrities who have it (Motakef et al., 2014), no literature was actually able to provide insight into the way this stigma perpetuates in live cosmetic surgery consultations until recently (Padley 2024). Furthermore, little to no evidence has been gathered to date regarding the communicative implications of identifying the use of stigmatising and shaming language in such consultations and how healthcare practitioners may perceive this. Therefore, these results demonstrate that two thirds of the surgeons involved in the study were surprised by such results and perhaps had not considered how “hiding” the procedure may actually increase stigmatisation of the field and of the patient.

The surgeons also offered the following comments during the debriefing sessions on this topic.

- (1) *This was perhaps quite a revelation. We always think that this is a good thing [obtaining natural and unnoticeable results] and something to aim for but alas it is just exacerbating the very thing we want to avoid—stigma.*
- (2) *I always advise and pursue a natural look.*

The first comment (1) highlights the importance of this finding to the surgeon as he claims that he had not considered the implications of encouraging the natural effect to the extent that it may be stigmatising the patient due to the element of 'hiding'. Furthermore, the use of the term 'revelation' even further stresses how surprising this linguistic observation is. On the other hand, the second comment (2)—made by a different surgeon—seems to indicate an indifference to such a finding as he states that this is what he always advises (as is usual practice in plastic surgery—i.e., obtaining the most pleasing natural aesthetic results). Therefore, this surgeon seems to place greater importance on the final result rather than the means by which this result is communicated (and the potential consequences of such).

The second key area of results provided to the clinicians is that which regards the use of medical lexis and layman terminology during their consultations. Indeed, participants were asked if they were surprised to discover the actual amount of medical lexis used during their consultations (Figure 2).

Figure 2.

Pie Chart Illustrating the Surgeons' Surprise Regarding Their use of Medical Terminology

Figure 2 shows that the same number of surgeons were surprised to discover that they did actually use medical terminology during their consultations (67%). This surprise is likely related to the fact that the recommendations regarding communication in medical consultations is to avoid any kind of

technical terminology in order to favour clarity and comprehension (Fage-Butler & Anesa, 2016; Fage-Butler & Nisbeth Jensen, 2016). Hence, their use of medical terminology could be indicative of an increased position of interactional power (Fairclough, 1989). Therefore, the surgeons were asked to comment on the appropriateness of their usage (Figure 3).

Figure 3.

Pie Chart Illustrating the Surgeons' Self-Assessment of Their Medical Terminology Usage

The pie chart (Figure 3) suggests that surgeons believe that their use of medical terminology is either appropriate (75%) or excessive (25%). Therefore, it would seem that despite their surprise regarding using medical lexis, on reading the extracts of their consultations (provided to them in the executive report), they believe that, on the whole, the terminology used is clear enough for patients to comprehend and, hence, has been clarified adequately when used.¹ It could also be stated that in some cases, they believe that their use of scientific lexis is excessive and hence should be modified in some way.

The additional comments made by the surgeons on the topic are the following:

- (3) *I think sometimes there are no lay terms to use to describe certain features or ideas or operation details. Medical terminology should be followed up with detailed explanations in different lay terms and preferably with diagrams to enhance the understanding of the patient. This is particularly important with descriptions of operations. I was just surprised by how frequently we use medical terminology in consultations.*
- (4) *Clients increasingly are exposed to and are more aware of medical terminology so it can be useful to introduce it.*

Comment (3) reveals that the clinician believes using medical terminology to be inevitable but that when it is used, it should be accompanied by further elaboration and/or explanation. Furthermore, it would seem that the surgeon found these results to be noteworthy also due to the fact that the terms used have been quantified. Hence, they are able to relate the observations to concrete statistics (which were also accompanied by a statistically significant p value). Comment (4) instead highlights that healthcare communication is indeed evolving and patients are becoming more literate (Fage-Butler & Anesa, 2016), hence, medical terminology now does have a place in consultation settings (Padley, 2025).

The final area of quantitative investigation presented to the surgeons was that of interruptions and their classification according to Goldberg's (1990) scale of neutral to dominant (power interruptions). Surgeons were all actually surprised that patients interrupted more than they did and they also stated that in 100% of the cases, the physician can be considered as the dominant figure. Therefore, it is possible to identify that from a societal positioning of dominance, the physicians perceive this traditional standing (Fairclough, 1989)—i.e., the doctor is the dominant figure within a medical consultation. Indeed, this also emerges due to the recognition of the fact that they are surprised by the more frequent interruption by patients as this does not meet their perception nor expectation of the consultation.

The final overall point investigated by this project regards the tangibility and applicability of the results (Sarangi, 2006) and whether the use of corpus linguistic methodologies for healthcare communication (Brookes & Collins, 2023) is deemed to produce relevant results for healthcare professionals. Therefore, the questionnaire measured the physicians' impressions of the executive report in terms of utility. Indeed, 100% of the participants stated that they found the results 'Very Useful' and to the question 'Are these findings useful enough to consider changing your communicative practice?' 100% of the respondents answered 'Yes'. Therefore, for this small sample of respondents, the corpus linguistic results were deemed to be relevant and applicable to their own communicative practice.

The surgeons offered some of the following comments in terms of their intended change to their communication:

- (5) *I would like to de-emphasise the importance I attach to obtaining the so called "natural looking" results so that other people don't know that the patient has had cosmetic surgery. I will put it in different terms / words rather than blanketly agreeing with the patient that that is the desirable objective or the ultimate objective. It can be one of the objectives but I will now explain to them that even if the surgery is noticeable to others it doesn't matter. What matters is whether they like it or not, and whether I have achieved what they are looking for. That they should not do it to please others or so that they don't attract attention or comment from others.*
- (6) *I will also encourage them to be less bothered about stigma and ignore people who make unhelpful or discouraging comments/ remarks; as often it is just people who cannot afford the surgery.*
- (7) *I will try and give the patients more time to talk in clinic and interrupt them less. I was also surprised by how often, as surgeons, we interrupt patients during the consultation.*
- (8) *I will now routinely ask if they understand what I mean when I use a medical term after I have finished explaining the term(s).*
- (9) *I will continue to use diagrams to pictorially assist the understanding of patients' understanding of their planned or requested surgery or the options available to them. This is something that patients repeatedly provide unsolicited feedback as being very useful to them in their understanding of the operations. This visual aid is therefore also an excellent method of communication.*

These comments are communication plans that one of the surgeons made in terms of how they intend to slightly alter their communicative strategies during consultations. Comment (5) demonstrates that the surgeon is aware of the importance that stigma and shame plays in society, and they will move the emphasis from achieving a 'natural look' to be one of the goals but not the main goal. Comment (6) also supports this and proves that the research presented to the healthcare professionals did in fact raise awareness regarding the stigma attached to cosmetic surgery.

In terms of the quantitative results presented to the surgeons (medical lexis used and the number of interruptions), comments (7-9) also would seem to show that the surgeon has become more aware of their communicative practice and intends to make some slight future adjustments based on the results presented.

Finally, during one of the online debriefing sessions, the following comments were made:

- (10) *I think carefully about how much I interrupt and try to give patients as much talking time as possible.*
- (11) *I'm more aware of my use of scientific words and I try to check comprehension more. Thank you for drawing my attention to it.*

Comments (10) and (11) both illustrate that the results from the linguistic project have led to current change in the clinicians' communicative practice and that they are now more reflective on these particular areas.

Therefore, overall the results are positively received by the clinicians and would appear to be of relevance in terms of their current and future communicative practice in their consultations. Hence, corpus linguistic methodology seems to offer applicable feedback to healthcare professionals and may also mean that educators can better prepare future practitioners to navigate complex patient interactions through similar methodologies.

5. Discussion

5.1. Implications for healthcare communication

The findings of this study have potential significant implications for healthcare communication practices and linguistic research. In particular, this paper investigated the extent to which a mixed methods qualitative-quantitative approach incorporating corpus linguistic methodologies could render viable and tangible communicative results for healthcare professionals.

Indeed, from an applied linguistics standpoint, the doctoral project hoped to implement Sarangi's (2006) 'effective linguistics'—i.e., offer findings to the non-linguist participants that are accessible, comprehensible and applicable to their field. While the doctoral project did not go beyond writing the executive report and scheduling the debriefing sessions with the clinicians, this study served to demonstrate what the perceptions of these latter two cases were as a post-doctoral line of pursuit.

The results would seem to show that the participants were made aware of their communicative practices, in line with the same lines of investigation that were explored in the doctoral thesis, (i.e., stigmatising discourses during the consultations, the use of medical lexis versus laity, the frequency and type of interruption and the use of the latter two in terms of interactional power balances). It is also likely that the surgeons found the quantitative results of a robust nature as they made use of statistical analysis in order to investigate the quantifiable linguistic features identified. Therefore, the results were

perceived as being relevant and informative in terms of communicative practices.

The relevancy to the healthcare practitioners themselves has been identified in the results through:

1. The expression of surprise regarding the three research areas—i.e., proof that these results did raise awareness for the surgeons and drew attention to these communicative features of their discourse (also from a quantifiable perspective).
2. The participants explicitly stated that the results had impacted on their intended communicative practice and communicative goals were set.
3. The debriefing sessions confirmed that some interactive changes had already been implemented, particularly on a level of awareness regarding the results identified in this project.

This study served to show that, from a methodological perspective, this kind of multi-methods and multidisciplinary research can be of use to the field of healthcare communication. Therefore, it serves to prove that the field of linguistics, which was previously often conceived as being overly ‘granular’ and of little relevance to clinicians (Sarangi, 2006) can be considered as accessible and of interest to healthcare professionals, particularly when incorporating quantitative results. Hence, the very use of corpus linguistics and statistical analyses would seem to be a point of strength for this study, as has been suggested in more recent times by other corpus linguists in the field (Brookes & Collins, 2023).

5.2. Study limitations

This project was carried out by a single researcher who recruited the surgeons during the SARS-COV-2 pandemic (period between 2020-2021). This led to a limited number of participants (i.e., three cosmetic surgery clinics and three respective surgeons). Furthermore, the use of corpus linguistic methodologies allows for generalisations to be made in terms of linguistic patterns but is more effective when applied to large datasets (more easily obtainable with written corpora). This project is made up of a spoken corpus and, hence, is a more specialised and smaller corpus. However, regardless of such limitations, accessing and recording live doctor-patient consultations is always a challenging task (Brookes & Collins, 2023), and the corpus can be considered large enough (for a spoken corpus) to be able to carry out viable corpus linguistic analysis. Furthermore, the project provides a peek into the ‘blackbox’ of clinical communication (Brookes & Hunt, 2021).

5.3. Study strengths and recommendations for practice

As mentioned in the previous section this study contributes to the field of corpus linguistics studies and healthcare communication through the collection of a spoken corpus of doctor-patient interaction (not easily obtainable). Furthermore, it also makes a relevant contribution to the field of applied linguistics (Candlin & Candlin, 2003; Sarangi, 2006; 2010) while also offering an appraisal of the methods used in order to achieve such results. In that sense, it considers the extent to which the results are judged as relevant to the clinicians and addressed the ‘so what?’ factor in terms of transferability and applicability of the results. Therefore, in the vein of applied linguistics as a field which should offer ‘effective linguistics’ (Sarangi, 2006), and based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made for improving communication in cosmetic surgery consultations:

- (1) **Addressing Stigma in Consultations:** Healthcare providers should be equipped to recognise and address stigma associated with cosmetic procedures. This includes creating an atmosphere where patients feel comfortable discussing their motivations and concerns without fear of judgement.
- (2) **Training in Patient-Centred Communication:** Medical professionals should receive training that emphasises the importance of patient-centred communication. This training should focus on active listening, empathy, and the use of lay terminology to ensure that patients feel heard and understood.
- (3) **Continuous Feedback Mechanisms:** Establishing continuous feedback mechanisms can help healthcare professionals reflect on their communication practices. Regularly reviewing consultations with colleagues or through peer feedback can foster an environment of improvement and learning.
- (4) **Multidisciplinary Collaboration:** Engaging with professionals from various disciplines—such as psychology, sociology, and linguistics—can enrich healthcare communication practices. Interdisciplinary collaboration can provide a broader perspective on the factors that influence patient interactions and decision-making.

6. Conclusion

This study provides valuable insights into the complexities of communication within cosmetic surgery consultations. The application of corpus linguistics as a methodological framework has yielded tangible, statistically robust results that can inform both clinical practice and pedagogical approaches in healthcare

communication. The findings indicate a need for ongoing research in this area to further understand the implications of language use in healthcare settings.

The research underscores the importance of communication in shaping patient experiences and perceptions. By enhancing the skills of healthcare professionals in this area, it is possible to improve the quality of care provided to patients seeking cosmetic procedures. As healthcare continues to evolve, the integration of linguistic insights into practice could be deemed as essential for fostering effective doctor-patient relationships and ensuring positive health outcomes.

Notes

1. Please note that the ways in which medical lexis has been used by the surgeons (and clarified or otherwise) is beyond the linguistic scope of this study but can be consulted in another publication (see Padley, 2025).

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References

- Atkins, S. (2019). Assessing health professionals' communication through roleplay: An interactional analysis of simulated versus actual general practice consultations. *Discourse Studies*, 21(2), 109-134. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461445618819396>
- Baker, P. (2006). *Using corpora in discourse analysis*. Continuum.
- Baker, P. (2023). *Using corpora in discourse analysis*. Bloomsbury.
- Brookes, G., & Baker, P. (2022). Cancer services patient experience in England: Quantitative and qualitative analyses of the National Cancer Patient Experience Survey. *BMJ Supportive and Palliative Care*. <https://doi.org/10.1136/spcare-2022-003543>
- Brookes, G., & Collins, L. C. (2023). *Corpus linguistics for health communication: A guide for research*. Routledge.
- Brookes, G., & Hunt, D. (2021). Discourse and health communication. In G. Brookes & D. Hunt (Eds.), *Analysing health communication: Discourse approaches* (pp. 1-17). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-73410-0_1
- Candlin, C. N., & Candlin, S. (2003). Healthcare communication: A problematic site for applied linguistics research. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 23, 134-135. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0267190503001376>
- Candlin, C., & Sarangi, S. (2004). Making applied linguistics matter. *Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 1(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1558/japl.v1.i1.1>
- Di Pace, B., & Padley, R. H. (2024). Enhancing treatment compliance in breast cancer patients: A multi-faceted approach. *Journal of Surgical Oncology*, 130(1), 38-39. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jso.27679>
- Duranti, A., & Goodwin, C. (1992). *Rethinking context: Language as an interactive phenomenon*. Cambridge University Press.
- Egbert, J., & Baker, P. (2020). *Using corpus methods to triangulate linguistic analysis*. Routledge.
- Fage-Butler, A. M., & Anesa, P. (2016). Discursive construction and negotiation of laity on an online health forum. *Pragmatics and Society*, 7(2), 196-216.

- Fage-Butler, A. M., & Nisbeth Jensen, M. (2016). Medical terminology in online patient-patient communication: Evidence of high health literacy? *Health Expectations: An International Journal of Public Participation in Health Care and Health Policy*, 19(3), 643-653.
- Fairclough, N. (1989). *Language and Power*. Longman.
- Goldberg, J. (1990). Interrupting the discourse on interruptions. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 14(6), 883-903. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-2166\(90\)90055-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-2166(90)90055-5)
- Gotti, M., Maci, S. M., & Sala, M. (2015). *The language of medicine: Science, practice and academia*. CELSB.
- Gumperz, J. J. (1999). On interactional sociolinguistic method. In S. Sarangi & C. Roberts (Eds.), *Talk, work and institutional order* (pp. 453-471). Mouton de Gruyter.
- Hunt, D. (2021). Corpus linguistics: Examining tensions in general practitioners' views about diagnosing and treating depression. In G. Brookes & D. Hunt (Eds.), *Analysing health communication: Discourse approaches* (pp. 459-465). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Lirola, M. M., & Chovanec, J. (2012). The dream of a perfect body come true: Multimodality in cosmetic surgery advertising. *Discourse and Society*, 23(5), 487-507.
- Maynard, D. W. (1991). Interaction and asymmetry in clinical discourse. *The American Journal of Sociology*, 97(2), 448-495.
- McEnery, T., & Hardie, A. (2012). *Corpus linguistics: Method, theory and practice*. Cambridge University Press.
- McMahon, S. A., & Winch, P. J. (2018). Systematic debriefing after qualitative encounters: An essential analysis step in applied qualitative research. *BMJ Global Health*, 3, e000837. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2018-000837>
- Moran, C., & Lee, C. (2013). Selling genital cosmetic surgery to healthy women: A multimodal discourse analysis of Australian surgical websites. *Critical Discourse Studies*, 10(4), 373-391.

- Motakef, S., Motakef, S., Chung, M. T., Ingargiola, M. J., & Rodriguez-Feliz, J. (2014). The cosmetic surgery stigma: An American cultural phenomenon? *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*, 134(5), 854e-855e. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PRS.0000000000000604>
- Mullany, L. (2007). *Gendered discourse in the professional workplace*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Padley, R. H. (2022a). Shame, discrimination and disability: Unveiling narratives of obesity. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(4), 43-64.
- Padley, R. H. (2022b). The use of authentic consultation recordings in the English for medical purposes classroom. *Scripta Manent*, 18(2), 21-41.
- Padley, R. H. (2024). "You won't be able to tell it's been done": A linguistic analysis of stigma in cosmetic surgery. *MediAzioni*, 43, A144-A163. <https://doi.org/10.6092/issn.1974-4382/20540h>.
- Padley, R. H. (2025). Navigating medical lexis. A digital era and shifting patient expertise. In G. Tessuto, S. M. Maci & M. J. Zerbo (Eds.), *Communicating medical science in the digital age: Culture, knowledge, expertise, practices*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing. <https://www.cambridge-scholars.com/product/978-1-0364-4566-9>
- Patel, A. (2010). Defeating the negative stereotypes of plastic surgery. *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*, 126(2), 116e-117e. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PRS.0b013e3181df6529>
- Roberts, C. (2003). Applied linguistics applied. In S. Sarangi & T. van Leeuwen (Eds.), *Applied linguistics and communities of practice* (pp. 132-149). Continuum.
- Roberts, C., & Sarangi, S. (2003). Uptake of discourse research in interprofessional settings: Reporting from medical consultancy. *Applied Linguistics*, 24(3), 338-359. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/24.3.338>
- Roter, D. L., & Hall, J. A. (2006). *Doctors talking with patients/patients talking with doctors: Improving communication in medical visits*. Praeger.
- Sarangi, S. (2006). The conditions and consequences of professional discourse studies. In R. Kiely, G. Clibbon, P. Rea-Dickins & H. Woodfield (Eds.), *Language, culture and identity in applied linguistics* (pp. 199-220). Equinox Publishing.

- Sarangi, S. (2010). Healthcare interaction as an expert communicative system. In J. Streeck (Ed.), *New adventures in language and interaction* (pp. 167-197). John Benjamins Publishing.
- Stubbe, M., Dew, K., Macdonald, L., & Dowell, A. (2021). Interactional sociolinguistics: Tracking patient-initiated questions across an episode of care. In G. Brookes & D. Hunt (Eds.), *Analysing health communication: Discourse approaches* (pp. 49-80). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-73410-0_3
- Swales, J. (1990). *Genre analysis: English in academic and research settings*. Cambridge University Press.
- West, C. (1984). *Routine complications*. Indiana University Press.